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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS.....	10
Shakirxodjayeva Zuxra Rustamxanovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	16
Aliyeva Zilola Mamatvalyevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTORS IN TASHKENT CITY.....	23
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
GREEN BONDS VS. SUSTAINABILITY LINKED LOANS: WHICH WORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONISATION?	29
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ БАНКА.....	34
Маликова Дилрабо Муминовна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELLING OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	42
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
AN INTEGRAL INDEX METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT POTENTIAL OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES	49
Sayyora Bakhtiyorovna Nazirova	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЕ, ПУБЛИЧНЫЕ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГРАНИЦЫ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ.....	53
Срождидинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING SYSTEM (SMART CONTRACTS, DECENTRALIZED DATABASE, AND AUDIT TRAILS).....	58
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	65
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF LABOR RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN SURXONDARYO REGION.....	72
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH ACROSS THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN USING INTENSITY COEFFICIENTS AND CLUSTER ANALYSIS.....	77
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING AGRIVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN UZBEKISTAN	85
Jabborov Shaymurod Akram o'g'li	
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li	
Atoyeva Mohinur Amrilloevna	
Avazov Jonibek Azizbek o'g'li	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА НА ТРАЕКТОРИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	91
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
FINANCING GREEN PROJECTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS	97
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	

FORMULA-BASED DISTRIBUTION OF INTERGOVERNMENTAL TRANSFERS TO LOCAL BUDGETS IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE SIMULATION ANALYSIS BASED ON 2026 FORECAST INDICATORS.....	103
Umidjon Pardaev	
Sarvar Maxmudov	
GOVERNMENT FUNDING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES: FINANCIAL PROMOTION MECHANISMS.....	115
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FORECASTING EXPORT AND IMPORT INDICATORS OF BUKHARA REGION	122
Ergashev Mirjon Yorqin o'g'li	
A CUSTOMER-ORIENTED INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGICAL MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY	130
Bakayev Ziyovuddinkhan Toshbolta ogli	
A PESTLI ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	139
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN	146
Khikmatullayeva Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi	
CHANGE MANAGEMENT DURING QUALITY ASSURANCE REFORM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	154
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
СТРАТЕГИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	162
Каримова Дилафруз Садриддин кизи	
E-COMMERCE AS A DIGITAL FORM OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES	167
Eshbayeva Shahnoza Fakhriddinovna	
ADVANTAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AN OCCUPATIONAL AND SKILLS MAPPING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN'S LABOUR MARKET	172
S.B.Goyipnazarov	
S.M.Kurbanbaeva	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FIXED ASSETS UTILIZATION IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	178
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING RESOURCE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF A GREEN ECONOMY.....	183
Karimov Islombek Bekpolat o'g'li	
THE IMPACT OF ECOTOURISM ON REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	
Samiev Siroj Saitovich	
Ochilova Guli Rashid kizi	
THE IMPACT OF RISK ALLOCATION ON INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) PROJECTS	197
Khaydarova Charos Nizomiddinovna	
PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX.....	202
Bohtaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ.....	209
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
ENHANCING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN THE POST-CRISIS ERA:	

AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	215
Foziljon Rustamov Xazratkulovich	
CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	219
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
THE PECULIARITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL AREAS.....	225
Makhliyo Umarova	
CHALLENGES OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR RESOLUTION.....	231
Aloviddin Zayniddinov Zayniddin ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF SUCCESSFUL AGROTOURISM DESTINATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	237
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani o'g'li	
ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL.....	247
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	
ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE FACTORS SHAPING IT: THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION.....	254
Djurayeva Munira Sadilloevna	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE ECONOMY OF BUKHARA REGION AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT TRENDS: AN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND REGIONAL CONCENTRATION.....	261
Azizjon Anvarovich Kadirov	
Nigina Djurayevna Yusupova	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BORDER TRANSPORT SYSTEMS.....	268
Ikromov Elyor Ibodulloevich	
ПУТИ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ АУДИТОРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	273
Бобонарова Камола	
GREEN BONDS AND SOVEREIGN DEBT INSTRUMENTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET RENEWAL: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS.....	278
Suleimanov Farrukh	
ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES.....	286
Qudratova Gulzoda Mahmudovna	
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	291
Munisa Abdurakhmonova	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH BASED ON THE COBBDOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A CASE STUDY OF SURXONDARYA REGION.....	296
Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	302
Kamola Saidova	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ВНУТРЕННЕГО АУДИТА В БЮДЖЕТНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ.....	307
Сайтмуратов Сайтмурат Машарип угли	
A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE IMPACT OF INTERMEDIATION SERVICES ON BANK PERFORMANCE AND ITS STATISTICAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	314
Miraxmedov Jasur Isroilovich	
EMPLOYER BRANDING IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW TO BECOME AN EMPLOYER OF CHOICE FOR TALENT.....	320
Doniyorova Fotimabonu Alisher qizi	

FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	325
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	331
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL COSTS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTITIES BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS.....	336
Sa'dullayeva Sayyora Nasillo qizi	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC APPROACHES AND BARRIERS TO THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	341
Samieva Gulnoza Tokhirovna	
THE IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF LABOR POTENTIAL ON THE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A REGION (A case study of the Khorezm region).....	348
Kutlimuratov Mansurbek Sattarovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF CLUSTERING TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	354
Asadbek Eshniyozov	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	358
Abdullaev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	
THE ROLE OF 5G TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES	366
Saidqosimova Umida Ibragimovna	
DIGITAL PLATFORMS AND THE EFFICIENCY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	371
Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTEREST RATE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Seitnazarov Daniyar Bakhadyrovich	
METHODOLOGY AND WAYS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	385
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF TRANSFORMATION	391
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	395
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ РЕГИОНОВ КАК ФАКТОР ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	399
Бутаева Сабина Холиёровна	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES IN INCREASING THE BRAND CAPITAL OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES	404
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECT FINANCING UNDER PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS (PPP)	416
Shodiev Akmal O'ktamjon ugli	
IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT	422
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
BLOCKCHAIN AND IOT FOR DIGITAL TRACKING OF FOOD EXPORTIMPORT FLOWS.....	426
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna	
Najmiddinov Yakhyo Fazliddin ugli	

THE PAYBACK PERIOD METHOD IN PERSONAL FINANCE: APPLICATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING	438
Akhunova Elena Anvarovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ADAPTIVE FIBONACCI STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS MODEL FOR GOLD TRADING: EVIDENCE FROM THE XAU/USD MARKET	447
Tukmirzaev Kamol Mumin ugli	
DEVELOPING MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL TRADE THROUGH A BRAND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: DIRECTIONS AND STRATEGIC PRIORITIES.....	455
Shohboz Ro‘zimatov Hamdambek o‘g‘li	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	461
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	466
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ НАУЧНЫХ ВЗГЛЯДОВ НА РОЛЬ СФЕРЫ УСЛУГ В ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	472
Усманов Фарзод Шохрухович	
STRATEGIC INSIGHTS FOR UZBEKISTAN’S RURAL DIGITALIZATION: LESSONS FROM THE SPATIAL SPILLOVER EFFECTS OF CHINA’S DIGITAL ECONOMY	481
Zhang Zhe	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ	487
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING SERVICE INFRASTRUCTURE EFFICIENCY: EVIDENCE FROM KASHKADARYA REGION	493
Azimov Islom	
ASSESSING DIGITAL GOVERNANCE EFFECTIVENESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	498
Berdiyev Temurbek Makhmudullo ugli	
РАЗРАБОТКА ИНТЕГРАЛЬНОГО ИНДЕКСА КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ (CGI) ДЛЯ БАНКОВ С ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ УЧАСТИЕМ.....	506
Жумадуллаева Дурдона Шухрат кизи	
DIGITAL ECONOMY-BASED GOVERNANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: LEVERAGING AI AND DATA FOR IMPROVED INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE	512
Olimjonov Abbosjon Olimjonovich	
THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT ON NATIONAL ECONOMIC COMPETITIVENESS.....	517
Baymuradov Shokhrukh Makhmudovich	
FACTORS INFLUENCING TAX REVENUE EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.....	522
Jurayev Xusan Atamuratovich	
THE ESSENCE, TASKS, AND INTERNATIONAL APPROACHES OF INTERNAL AUDIT IN LEASING TRANSACTIONS.....	536
Sadritdinov Bakhodir Bakhtiyarovich	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN THE MINING SECTOR.....	543
Oybekova S.K.	
METHODOLOGY FOR REFLECTING GOODWILL, INTANGIBLE ASSETS, AND INVESTMENTS IN CONSOLIDATION.....	548
Maxmudova Nargiza Davlyat qizi	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY:	

CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	554
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
THE DMED INFORMATION SYSTEM AS A FOUNDATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL E-HEALTH SYSTEM	561
Omonov Olim Murodullayevich	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN GLOBAL MARKETS	566
Safarova Muxabbat Radjabovna	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SUPPLY SYSTEM OF NURSERY FARMS	573
Abdufarmonov Farrux Faxriddinovich	
APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TOURISM MARKET AND ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PLATFORM ECONOMY.....	580
Jumayev Bobomurod Nurmaxmat o'g'li	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ «ЖЕНСКОГО» ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ.....	586
Холбаева Сабина Рустамовна	
ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ПРИОРИТЕТНЫХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ С УЧЁТОМ ЗАРУБЕЖНОГО ОПЫТА В МАЛОМ И СРЕДНЕМ БИЗНЕСЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	595
Камбарова Шахнозахон Мирвахитовна	
ISSUES OF EFFECTIVELY UTILIZING REGIONAL EXPORT POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN	603
Umaraliyev Sarvar Rustamovich	
TERRITORIAL DISPROPORTIONS IN TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE OF THE JIZZAKH REGION AND THEIR IMPACT ON TOURIST FLOWS.....	610
A.Sh. Daliev	
T.Sh. Muxiddinov	
METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO HOUSING CONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN: INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP MECHANISMS.....	616
Mirumar Abdulla Ugli Usmonov	
IMPROVEMENT OF COST ACCOUNTING AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS IN THE FISHERY INDUSTRY: PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR THE ADAPTATION OF IFRS, ECONOMETRIC MODELING, AND ESG REPORTING FOR FISHERY CLUSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	620
Shodiev Aslam Rakhmatilloevich	
Alikulov Abdumumin Ismatovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP FRUIT PROCESSING ENTERPRISES BASED ON THE CLUSTER SYSTEM	627
Yusufova Laylo G'ayrat qizi	
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MODERN BANKING SERVICE DEVELOPMENT	635
Mamutova Ayygul Kalmurzaevna	
IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED AUDIT TECHNIQUES (CAATS) AND ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES IN THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS.....	642
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS AND THE FORMATION OF KEY AUDIT MATTERS (ISA 701)	649
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	656
Abdullayev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN SERICULTURE DEVELOPMENT: ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS APPLICABLE TO UZBEKISTAN.....	664
Janikulova Lobar Shakarbaevna	
SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE THROUGH ESG AND ENERGY MANAGEMENT: A GREEN MARKETING PERSPECTIVE	670
Khaydarova Kamola Axinjanovna	
SYSTEM AND STRATEGY FOR HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN AN ORGANIZATION	675
Azimov Tolmas Nematullayevich	
MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF SMALL BUSINESSES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	682
Abdusalim Shavkatov	
STRUCTURE AND DYNAMICS OF BANK LOANS	689
Jorayeva Zarifa	
THE IMPORTANCE OF USING MODERN APPROACHES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF BUSINESS PROCESSES OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	698
Djumaniyazova Mo‘tabarkhan Ravshanbekovna	

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THE IMPORTANCE OF USING MODERN APPROACHES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF BUSINESS PROCESSES OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. This article examines the importance of using modern approaches in the management of business processes in textile enterprises. In particular, the study substantiates the necessity and practical relevance of transitioning from a task-based approach to a process-based approach in business process management. The article highlights that the process-based approach contributes to improving management efficiency, optimizing internal operations, enhancing coordination among structural units, and increasing the competitiveness of textile enterprises.

Keywords: business process, management, task-based approach, process-based approach, textile enterprises.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается значение применения современных подходов к управлению бизнес-процессами текстильных предприятий. Особое внимание уделено обоснованию необходимости и практической целесообразности перехода от функционально-задачного подхода к процессному подходу в управлении бизнес-процессами. Показано, что внедрение процессного подхода способствует повышению эффективности управления, оптимизации внутренних процессов, улучшению взаимодействия между структурными подразделениями и укреплению конкурентоспособности текстильных предприятий.

Ключевые слова: бизнес-процесс, управление, функционально-задачный подход, процессный подход, текстильные предприятия.

INTRODUCTION

The textile industry occupies an important place in the economy of Uzbekistan, providing a significant share of industrial output, employment, and export revenues. In recent years, this sector has entered a stage of rapid modernization. In particular, since 2017, following the implementation of economic reforms and currency market liberalization, Uzbekistan has gradually shifted from exporting raw cotton to producing and exporting finished textile products. This transformation has become one of the key directions of structural change in the industry.

In these conditions, the need to develop a management system that is responsive to market changes has increased significantly. Therefore, the transition of textile enterprises from a traditional functional and task-based management approach to a more progressive process-based approach is of particular scientific and practical importance. Substantiating the effectiveness of this transition from a scientific perspective is an urgent task for improving the competitiveness and sustainable development of textile enterprises.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Fundamental changes in the global economy in the second half of the twentieth century created the basis for the further development of management theory and practice. One of the scholars who made a significant contribution to the development of management theory was Henri Fayol. In his approach, “management” was described as a sequence of interrelated processes, while “administration” was considered one of the six main types of organizational activity. Thus, Fayol substantiated the transition from a task-oriented approach to a process-oriented understanding of management, emphasizing the importance of the sequence of actions in organizing managerial activity [1].

The standardization of management processes creates broad opportunities for applying the process approach in management. In this regard, the proposals developed by G. Emerson are of particular importance. He proposed the principle of “standard written instructions” for organizing production activities in enterprises, thereby contributing to the development of systematic and process-based management practices [2].

Important scientific research on progressive approaches to management was carried out by W. Shewhart, E. Deming, and J. Juran. In particular, Edwards Deming emphasized the need to eliminate barriers between interrelated departments involved in the production process. He argued that most companies are formally organized according to functional structures, while in practice they must operate in an environment of mutual functional interaction. According to Deming, “processes violate hierarchical structures”, which clearly reflects the essence of process-oriented management [3; 4; 5].

Issues related to process management have also been studied by M. Porter [6], S. I. Bay [7], V. Pareto [8], P. Drucker [9], V. Repin [10], A. A. Tishchenko [11], R. Kaplan [12], and N.-G. Olve [13], as well as by other foreign and local researchers. Their works provide an important theoretical and methodological basis for understanding the role of business processes in improving enterprise efficiency and competitiveness.

Among Uzbek scholars, R. A. Isayev studied the conceptual foundations of integrated quality management and strategic management systems in textile industry enterprises, as well as the methodological aspects of their implementation [14; 15].

However, from a scientific perspective, the issue of business process management in textile industry enterprises has not yet been sufficiently studied. Therefore, the development of modern approaches to business process management in textile enterprises remains a relevant and priority research area.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of this scientific research is the dialectical method. In the research process, statistical analysis, selective observation, comparative analysis, and expert evaluation methods were also used. These methods made it possible to study the management of business processes in textile enterprises from both theoretical and practical perspectives, identify existing problems, and substantiate the necessity of applying modern process-based management approaches.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the current conditions of intense competition, ensuring adaptability to market changes and strengthening the competitiveness of textile industry enterprises require the improvement of business process management through the use of systemic reengineering technologies. In this regard, it is advisable to shift from a functional management approach to a process-based approach in the effective management of business processes in the textile industry.

The implementation of this approach provides several important opportunities. First, it allows enterprises to identify “pain points” in their main production business processes and to develop a system for diagnosing and forecasting business processes, thereby ensuring their continuous improvement. Second, it creates the basis for forming a new management system based on modern technologies, including digitalization and artificial intelligence.

At the current stage of development, many industrial enterprises are compelled to implement organizational measures aimed not only at maintaining their current market position but also at remaining competitive under conditions of strong competition. Such measures include optimizing production volumes, eliminating inefficient production links, developing new types of products, searching for promising market segments, and improving the use of labour resources. To implement these measures effectively,

enterprises increasingly use modern business process management technologies, such as Six Sigma, Total Quality Management (TQM), Total Productive Maintenance (TPM), the Toyota Production System (TPS), 5S, lean technologies, and other similar approaches.

Based on the objectives of the research, proposals for improving the management of the main production business processes of textile industry enterprises, particularly sewing and knitting enterprises, can be developed and implemented in the following sequence: conducting an in-depth strategic analysis of all areas of enterprise activity; developing a system for diagnosing and forecasting business processes; developing an enterprise development strategy, including the formulation of its mission and goals and the selection of the most appropriate strategic direction; selecting the most suitable alternative based on the results of streamlining business processes; describing the selected interrelated business processes; developing a strategic process map aimed at ensuring the integration of interrelated business processes; forming an improved business process management system and a team of responsible performers; implementing the newly developed business process and introducing improved management systems into the practice of sewing and knitting enterprises; developing a methodology for assessing the effectiveness of the business process management system and applying it in practice; and, based on the assessment results, regularly improving the system and developing measures to increase enterprise efficiency (Figure 1).

The results of the analysis of the current production, management, and financial situation of sewing and knitting enterprises, including "YUSTEX", "BETLIS TEKSTIL", and "FULL COTTON" limited liability companies, show that their ability to adapt to changes in the external environment through the effective use of internal opportunities is not yet at the required level. Under conditions of intense competition, the traditional linear-functional management structure used in these enterprises does not fully enable management to respond effectively to market changes and economic challenges.

In addition, the absence of a separate marketing department in the management structure of these sewing and knitting enterprises creates certain difficulties in forming an alternative product range that corresponds to consumer demand and market trends. Therefore, the introduction of a process-based management approach and the strengthening of marketing-oriented management mechanisms are important conditions for improving the competitiveness and sustainable development of textile enterprises.

Therefore, the current state of the management system makes it necessary to prioritize a process-based approach in the management of sewing and knitting enterprises. However, it should be noted that improving the management system through reengineering cannot be achieved solely through continuous improvement measures carried out by employees.

In enterprises such as "YUSTEX", "BETLIS TEKSTIL", and "FULL COTTON" limited liability companies, the simultaneous implementation of radical organizational changes across the entire management system may involve certain risks. Therefore, it is advisable to develop and implement pilot projects aimed at preparing and testing proposals for improving business process management in sewing and knitting enterprises.

Figure 1 presents a brief description of the stages of the algorithm for organizing process-oriented management of interrelated business processes in textile enterprises.

At the first stage, an in-depth strategic analysis of all areas of enterprise activity is carried out based on marketing principles and using methods of strategic analysis of the enterprise's market position. Based on the results of the analysis, conclusions are drawn regarding the internal capabilities of the enterprise and its ability to adapt to changes in the external environment. The issues of conducting marketing research on the internal and external environment of enterprises are widely covered in the scientific literature.

The second stage involves developing a system for diagnosing and forecasting the business processes of sewing and knitting enterprises. The practical application of the proposed diagnostic and forecasting system for textile enterprise business processes makes it possible to supplement the existing management accounting system with information necessary for making effective managerial decisions, including the selection of alternative solutions. At this stage, during the development of the model, it becomes possible to identify bottlenecks, duplication of functions, irrational use of resources, and other disruptions in business processes. The developed business process model should then be tested for compliance by top managers of the textile enterprise and highly qualified management specialists (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Stages of the algorithm for organizing process-oriented management of interconnected business processes of textile enterprises¹

At the third stage, the development strategy of the sewing and knitting enterprise is formulated. This includes defining the mission, setting strategic goals, and selecting the most appropriate development strategy. In the proposed approach, the mission of the sewing and knitting enterprise is developed on the basis of a three-dimensional coordinate system. The first axis, "necessity", reflects the results of the strategic analysis of the enterprise conducted on the basis of marketing research at the first stage. The second axis, "implementation opportunities", reflects an integrated assessment of the enterprise's existing internal capabilities and competencies in satisfying market needs. The third axis, "future orientation", expresses the business philosophy of the enterprise, including its aspirations, values, and principles.

On the basis of the three-dimensional spatial structure formed by the intersection of these coordinate axes, a "tree of goals" is developed. This includes strategic options, the goals and tasks of their implementation, and the stages of process realization. The issues of developing strategies for industrial enterprises are also widely covered in the scientific literature.

At the fourth stage, based on the results of streamlining the enterprise's business processes in accordance with the concept of diversification, the most appropriate alternative is selected, and the selected interrelated business processes are described.

At the fifth stage, the final strategic map of business processes selected for the implementation of the pilot project is developed. This map is aimed at ensuring the integration of interrelated business processes. In implementing this stage, proposals are developed for applying the Balanced Scorecard system in the formation of an effective management system, taking into account the production, management, and financial condition of the sewing and knitting enterprise.

¹ Author development

At the sixth stage, an effective team is formed, and an improved business process management system is developed in accordance with the theory of effective teams. In our opinion, the successful development and practical implementation of an improved management system based on the reengineering of relatively complex and new business processes depend directly on the cohesion of the team formed within the organizational structure of each manufacturing enterprise, as well as on the knowledge, skills, competence, and initiative of each team member.

In this process, the ideas of M. Belbin, J. Lewis, J. Stewart, and H. Rampersad on the use of sociometric methods can contribute to the development of technologies for forming a cohesive and initiative-oriented team. The proposed methodology suggests determining the boundaries of processes at the stages of the product life-cycle concept proposed by T. Levitt in relation to sewing and knitting enterprises, and forming teams based on the results obtained and the tasks performed. In this case, part of the tasks is transferred to employees of functional departments assigned to the team. Responsibility matrices and methods for describing the flow of the final business process, including the IDEF0 methodology, can be used as tools for transferring or outsourcing tasks.

At the seventh stage, newly developed business processes and improved management systems that meet the requirements of the value chain concept are implemented. Taking into account the specific features of business processes in sewing and knitting enterprises, it is considered appropriate to improve their business process management through the application of reengineering technology.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to improve the efficiency of business process management in sewing and knitting enterprises by transitioning from a task-based approach to a process-based management approach, the following recommendations are proposed:

Develop and successfully implement a methodology for assessing the effectiveness of business process management in sewing and knitting enterprises.

Group and describe the main business processes involved in the production of goods in sewing and knitting enterprises.

Develop an effective monitoring system for evaluating the efficiency of business process management in sewing and knitting enterprises.

Improve the diagnostic organizational mechanism aimed at ensuring the continuous development of business processes in textile enterprises.

Improve process management technology by developing a computerized system for diagnosing and forecasting business processes in textile enterprises.

Ensure the transition from a task-based management approach to a process-based approach through the use of diagnostics, methodological support, forecasting, and evaluation of the effectiveness of management resource utilization for the continuous development of business processes in textile enterprises.

Overall, the implementation of these recommendations will contribute to improving management efficiency, optimizing internal processes, increasing adaptability to market changes, and strengthening the competitiveness of sewing and knitting enterprises.

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